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Enhancing flash flood risk perception and awareness of mitigation actions through risk communication: A pre-post survey design

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1 **Enhancing flash flood risk perception and awareness of mitigation actions through risk**
2 **communication: A pre-post survey design**

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20 **ABSTRACT**

21
22 Flood risk management is gradually shifting from a risk-based approach to an integrated one
23 that, among other elements, considers risk communication (RC) as a means of boosting
24 resilience. Regardless of the above, few scientists have tackled up to now the integration of
25 RC into flood risk management. In this connection, this particular study seeks to check out the
26 potential of a risk dialogue approach (based on an ad hoc RC strategy) to change attitudes and
27 behaviours in relation to flash flood risk. Via a pre-post survey design, we evaluated risk
28 perception and awareness regarding a Civil Protection Plan (CPP) implemented locally (i.e.,
29 in the municipality of Navaluenga, central Spain). For this particular objective, a
30 questionnaire survey was created, and 201 adults (representing more than 10% of the
31 population census) were interviewed twice in a one-year period. Before the second survey, an
32 RC strategy was created. The RC strategy comprised briefings, quiz answers, storytelling, a
33 contest of videos and photographs about past floods, and an intergenerational workshop. A t-
34 test for paired sample analyses and a general linear model (GLM) repeated measures ANOVA
35 were applied to identify changes in risk perception and awareness. Our results indicate that
36 the RC strategy did increase flood risk perception in Navaluenga in the long term (lifetime).
37 Also, it increased the level of awareness of the various features that comprise the CPP,
38 enabling people to be more competent in facing a flash flood. Some cognitive biases detected
39 in the perceptual process of human beings may shed some light on the results obtained. The
40 implementation of well-thought-out RC strategies can play a role in improving resilience,
41 particularly in geographic areas such as the Iberian Peninsula, in which climate change
42 scenarios indicate a likely increase in the severity and frequency of flooding.

43

44 **KEYWORDS:** EU Flood Directive; flood risk; flood risk management; urban area; social
45 resilience; risk communication

46 **1. INTRODUCTION**
47

48 Mountainous river basins with a drainage area of up to a few hundred square kilometres quite
49 often respond quickly to heavy precipitation events and/or the orographic control of the spatial
50 distribution of rainfall intensity (Gaume and Borga, 2008; Lumbroso and Gaume, 2012). This
51 hydrological response is mainly due to the topographic relief, the steepness of slopes and,
52 consequently, the strong hydrological connectivity that characterizes these basins (Bodoque et
53 al., 2015). Additional physical attributes, like soil types, land uses and impervious area, together
54 with the degree of soil saturation before the flash flood occurs, will additionally condition the
55 flash flood potential of extreme precipitation events (Hapuarachchi et al., 2011). The ensuing
56 floods have a fast hydrological response, recognized by hydrographs showing steep rising and
57 falling limbs and, accordingly, short lag times. The above results in what are known as “flash
58 floods” due to their rapid onset, i.e., with only a few hours between rain falling and flooding
59 (Borga et al., 2007; Marchi et al., 2010; Naulin et al., 2013; Gourley et al., 2017) and, therefore,
60 the short warning times that lead to the majority of flood deaths worldwide (Barredo, 2007).
61 Therefore, the primary challenge in risk management is related to the short time available for
62 lessening the risk, which requires preparedness and response actions to be put into practice
63 (Bodoque et al., 2016a).

64
65 The approval of the EU Floods Directive (Directive 2007/60 / EC) has meant a change
66 concerning how studies on risk mitigation should be addressed (Hall et al., 2003; Serra-Llobet
67 et al., 2013). In this respect, until 2007 fragmented approaches to the problem were
68 developed. They were mainly based on partial analysis of the hazard, as usually only the
69 flooded area was considered (Hooijer et al., 2004). Also, risk mitigation was primarily based
70 on the design of structural measures (e.g., levees, reservoirs for flood attenuation), or to a
71 lesser extent on non-structural measures (e.g., civil protection plans (CPPs), land use

72 planning) (Merz et al., 2010). Specifically, structural measures followed a reactive approach,
73 so that once a catastrophic event had occurred, they were put in place to prevent flood risk
74 (Sayers et al., 2002). Decision-makers have mistakenly perceived these measures as
75 instruments to increase safety levels which has facilitated the development of different types
76 of land uses in the flood plain, thereby increasing flood risk i.e., levee effect or safe
77 development paradox (Tobin, 1995). The effectiveness of this total protection approach has
78 been questioned lately since, despite the significant investments made during recent decades,
79 the growth in flood damages has followed a clear positive trend (Bradford et al., 2012). The
80 above could be either as a result of flood events with a magnitude not considered during the
81 design of structural measures, or due to their poor design as uncertainty was not considered,
82 or it was characterized inadequately (Vis et al., 2003).

83
84 Since 2007 the application of the EU Floods Directive has involved the adoption of
85 comprehensive risk management schemes, which have been based on the premise that zero
86 risk situations do not exist (Kubal et al., 2009). Therefore, the ultimate goal of the measures to
87 be applied should be partial mitigation of risk, and they must be designed to diversify and
88 adapt different risk reduction strategies. This approach requires that the actions to be
89 developed must be continuously evaluated. To this end, they must be adequate in terms of
90 both the territory and its social context, which is a critical aspect as risk management based
91 simply on a technocratic approach may give people a false sense of security (Lawrence et al.,
92 2013). The foregoing is because the social dimension of flooding mainly related to the
93 subjective aspects of risk (i.e., emotional feelings, such as the fear, worry or trust that
94 individuals have concerning flood risk), which determines people's risk perception, is usually
95 not integrated into the risk management process (Birkholz et al., 2014). Within this context,
96 social resilience, i.e., the ability of groups or communities to cope with external stresses and
97 disruptions (Adger, 2000), provides a practical framework for addressing integrated risk

98 management schemes. Thus, the characterization of social resilience enables flood
99 preparedness and response to be improved as it facilitates the correct implementation of
100 mitigation actions to reduce the negative consequences of flash flooding (Bodoque et al.,
101 2016a). Lately, the concept of resilience has gained importance thanks to the impulse
102 provided by the Hyogo Framework for Action (in force until 2015) and the Sendai
103 Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction (to be developed during the period 2015–2030) in
104 which resilience is one of the global targets (Thieken et al., 2016; Horn and Elagib, 2018).

105
106 The analysis of risk perception, together with the design and implementation of RC strategies,
107 are critical stages in flood risk management since they facilitate the establishment of a
108 response to flood warnings and initiatives to boost community preparedness (Bubeck et al.,
109 2012; de Boer et al., 2015; Fox-Rogers et al., 2016; Morss et al., 2016). Understanding the
110 characteristics of local communities constitutes a priority to enhance social resilience. So, the
111 extent to which a community can show resilience after a flood largely depends on risk
112 perception, which is related to the social context in which a given flood event occurs (Wickes
113 et al., 2015). In addition, risk perception depends on different psychological variables,
114 including intuitive evaluation of risk and qualitative reflections such as fear and trust in
115 decision-makers (Figueiredo et al., 2009). Therefore, knowing how people perceive flood risk
116 is crucial in regard to fixing what aspects related to the flood risk management process should
117 be disseminated to enhance flood preparedness and, therefore, to increase social resilience by
118 ensuring that appropriate and effective measures for flood risk mitigation are taken (Bradford
119 et al., 2012). Nevertheless, both risk perception and RC are often neglected when developing
120 flood risk management, which means that management strategies have often failed, as
121 scientists and technicians can perceive flood risk in a very different way to how the public
122 perceives it. The first studies on risk perception go back to the 1940s (White, 1945). Most of

123 the research conducted on this topic so far has been of an exploratory nature. However, the
124 theoretical frame developed in the field of social sciences, i.e., psychometric paradigm
125 (Slovic, 1992) and heuristic approaches (Khaneman and Tversky, 1996), has usually been
126 neglected (Kellens et al., 2013).

127

128 The effectiveness of RC in improving community preparedness and awareness as part of
129 effective flood risk management plans has scarcely been studied. Previous work has mainly
130 focused on conceptual approaches. So, data from RC strategies were either used to understand
131 population perspectives on flood risks and mitigation (Haer et al., 2016; Lazrus et al., 2016)
132 or focused on the distinction between prevention and promotion (de Boer et al., 2015). Under
133 this general approach, the effectiveness of two-way and one-way RC strategies to improve
134 preparedness has also been assessed (Maidl and Buchecker, 2015). Other research focused on
135 determining how useful flood hazard maps (as RC tools) are regarding disaster prevention
136 awareness (Mizuki, 2012), or exploring how local managers use flood hazard maps for RC
137 purposes (Kjellgren, 2013). In addition, identification of RC gaps and the creation of
138 strategies to enhance information sharing have also been addressed (Stewart and Rashid,
139 2011).

140 Accordingly, the primary objective of the present study is to assess the degree to which RC
141 enables risk perception to be improved at the local level. Likewise, it intends to determine the
142 extent to which RC enhances the level of knowledge of civil protection and emergency
143 management strategies created with the primary objective of safeguarding people and assets
144 from the effects of flooding. So, the research undertaken here targeted the achievement of a
145 change in attitudes and behaviours through a risk dialogue approach (Demeritt and Nobert,
146 2014). To do so, an ad hoc RC strategy was designed and put into practice with the aim of
147 creating awareness (understood herein as people's awareness of actions that they should –

148 according to the CPP – take before, during and after a flash flood) of the reality of flash flood
149 risk and the existing risk mitigation tools. The effectiveness of this RC strategy was assessed
150 via a pre-post survey design, which consisted of two stages carried out through a
151 questionnaire survey by trained interviewers both previously and subsequently to the
152 implementation of the RC strategy.

153 2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

154 2.1. Study site

155 Navaluenga is situated in central Spain on the banks of the Alberche River and the Chorrerón
156 Stream (Fig. 1). According to the census of the Spanish Statistical Office, Navaluenga has a
157 population of 1,902 locals (data for 2017). Navaluenga has suffered flash flood events related
158 to the Alberche River and the Chorrerón Stream since at least the late Middle Ages, as
159 attested by existing historical documents (i.e., obtained from municipal and ecclesiastical
160 archives). The latest events in the 1990s and at the beginning of the 2000s caused
161 considerable economic losses and placed part of the local population at risk (Bodoque et al.,
162 2016a).

163 **Place Fig. 1 here**

164 Since Navaluenga has a medieval origin, with a compact urban structure made up of irregular
165 closed-street blocks, two-storey buildings are predominant, and over 50% of individuals
166 reside within the flooding zone. It is worth highlighting that the dependency ratio (i.e., a
167 measure indicating the number of dependents, aged zero to 14 and more than 65 years old, to
168 the entire population, aged 15 to 64) reaches 60%. Usually, the population of Navaluenga
169 expands substantially during the summer season when it gets to around 20,000 inhabitants.

170 Thus, the exposed population could multiply tenfold during the summer and could double or
171 even quintuple during holidays and at weekends (between 5,000 and 10,000 inhabitants).

172 The information source and strategy for building the CPP against flood risk in Navaluenga
173 were based on the Spanish legislation on this particular matter (Spanish Ministry of Justice,
174 2010). A far more detailed explanation of the CPP of Navaluenga can be read in Bodoque et
175 al. (2016a).

176 **2.2. Design of the RC strategy and procedures**

177
178 With the intention of improving the understanding of flood risk, including local people's degree
179 of awareness, an RC strategy was designed for the general public. Thus, different actions were
180 taken, such as the disclosure of detailed flood maps, informative talks, a contest of questions
181 and answers, storytelling, a contest of videos and photographs about past floods and an
182 intergenerational workshop on past floods. All these actions were designed from four basic
183 premises:

184
185 I. **In-depth knowledge of the flood hazard and risk of flooding.** There are detailed flood
186 maps, i.e., with a representation scale of 1:5,000 or 2x2 m spatial resolution (Fig. 2),
187 published for more than two decades from the early 1990s to the present day. So,
188 mapping of flood-prone areas is available for different return periods (i.e., 50, 100 and
189 500 years), in the form of a poster exhibited in the town hall building (since 1996).
190 Flood hazard maps published in several book chapters and papers in scientific/technical
191 journals are also available in the municipal library (from 1996 to 2001). New flood
192 hazard and flood risk maps, including cost-benefit analysis of mitigation measures, i.e.,
193 from 2008 to 2016 (Ballesteros-Cánovas et al., 2013; Bodoque et al., 2016b), have also
194 been produced. In addition, since 2014, flood hazard and risk maps have been available

195 on the Internet, such as those included in the National System of Floodable Areas
196 Cartography (MAPAMA, 2014) that meet the EU Flood Directive requirements for
197 procedures, contents and design.

198 **Place Fig. 2 here**

199
200 II. **Knowledge of the local social and associative reality** of Navaluenga, detecting the
201 primary social agents that can disseminate and streamline the plan (known as interested
202 parties, groups and organizations) (Trettin and Musham, 2000). For this purpose, an
203 attempt was made to involve the Town Council and the security forces, but also cultural
204 associations (e.g., juveniles, homemakers, retirees) and the committee for protection
205 and rescue at the local level. For this, the figure of an activity coordinator, born in the
206 locality and well known by everyone, was essential to involve a broad enough sector of
207 the population of Navaluenga. In this regard, Martens et al. (2009) highlighted the role
208 of the diversity of the people, which determines that RC has to be adapted based on how
209 different groups of individuals perceive risk.

210
211 III. **A detailed analysis of the results obtained in previous studies with the target**
212 **population**, identifying community groups (clusters) who needed improvement in
213 their knowledge of the CPP, and their socio-demographic profiles (see details in
214 Bodoque et al., 2016a), for example a large population sector with a lack of
215 knowledge of the CPP (group or cluster 2; see details in Bodoque et al. (2016a). Its
216 key features are: permanent residents (75%); mostly women (63%); aged 35–54
217 (51%); school age (high school, 46%); and access to the Internet. This approach is in
218 line with the proposals of Renn (Renn, 2005), which underscored the value of
219 adapting risk communication to the concrete needs of the people, and Basic (2009),
220 underlining the public's risk perception as a key factor in building effective RC

221 strategies.

222

223 IV. **A careful bibliographic review of the approaches followed by different RC**
224 **strategies**, with the intention of finding original and innovative activities that were
225 potentially applicable. To this end, we examined the compilations of experiences, such
226 as those collected in Kellens et al. (2013) and Morss et al. (2016).

227 RC covers a broad scope of exercises, such as encouraging interest in environmental issues,
228 increasing public awareness, influencing people's attitudes and behaviour, acting in emergency
229 situations, aiding in decision-making and assisting in conflict resolution (Boholm, 2008). Based
230 on this approach and the integration of the four basic premises previously stated, the design of
231 the RC strategy was based on five actions aimed at a specific target audience and using
232 attractive and original tools (Table 1).

233

234 **Place Table 1 here**

235

236 A pre-post survey design was adopted to test the impact of the RC strategy on risk perception
237 and awareness. It consisted of two stages carried out through a questionnaire survey. The
238 results of the first phase (February 2015) showed that both risk perception and level of
239 awareness were low in the majority of the sample (Bodoque et al., 2016a). The RC strategy
240 was applied in November 2015, and one month later the second stage was conducted
241 (December 2015–January 2016).

242

243 **2.3. Participants**

244

245 In the second phase, information was collected from 201 out of a total of 254 adults who
246 participated in the first phase (Bodoque et al., 2016a). Participants in the first survey were

247 selected using a quota sampling procedure (Robinson, 2014), in which age and gender were
248 used as control variables. In the second survey, the same individuals who participated in the
249 first round were contacted. For this, the last two numbers and the letter of their national
250 identity document were used as location criteria. In this second phase, conducted after the
251 implementation of the RC strategy, 79.1% of those who collaborated in the first survey
252 participated. This percentage is considered sufficient to establish comparisons between the
253 two surveys (1 and 2). Table 2 summarizes the main socio-demographic characteristics of the
254 people surveyed after implementing the RC strategy.

255

256

Place Table 2 here

257

258 A variable was generated to determine the degree of participation in the different activities
259 designed related to the RC strategy. It was based on three categories showing the level of
260 knowledge and involvement in the various RC activities: those who stated that they did not
261 know any of the activities of the RC strategy (19.9%); those who reported having heard of
262 some of the activities, but acknowledged that they had not participated in any (54.2%); and
263 those who reported having attended or participated in some of the RC activities (25.9%).

264

265 **2.4. Measures**

266

267 A questionnaire survey was designed and conducted by trained interviewers to analyse
268 changes in perceptions of flood risk and awareness after applying the RC strategy. The
269 questionnaire included the same measures employed in the first survey referring to these two
270 variables (Bodoque et al., 2016a). First, flood risk perception was assessed by adjusting a
271 general measure consisting of four items (Bourque et al., 2012) that considered the possible
272 risk of flooding in Navaluenga and homes themselves, both in the short term (the next five
273 years) and the long term (lifetime). The above was measured on a five-point Likert scale,

274 ranging from highly improbable to very likely. Second, changes in awareness were assessed
275 by inquiring about actions to take: a) before the flood to prevent negative consequences
276 (preparedness behaviour); b) during the flood (b.1. evacuation routes and meeting points, b.2.
277 self-protective actions and b.3. actions to take before leaving the dwelling; and c) after the
278 flood: actions taken in houses after flooding (See Table 3). Participants were asked whether
279 they knew what actions to take in each situation with a closed-ended question: yes or no. If
280 they answered yes (perceived awareness), they were asked what these were through an open-
281 ended question. The percentages of correct responses for each category, a), b) and c), were
282 drawn from those that coincided with the actions defined in the CPP. These percentages
283 measured the level of real awareness and were the variables used in the data analysis.

284
285 **Place Table 3 here**

286 287 **2.5. Data analysis**

288
289 The data obtained were analysed using the software IBM® SPSS® Statistics 19.0. A t-test for
290 paired sample analysis was used to compare the risk perception and the level of awareness
291 before and after the RC strategy. Next, aiming to evaluate the effect of the degree of
292 participation on risk perception and awareness, data were analysed by implementing a general
293 linear model (GLM) repeated measures ANOVA, with time (before and after) as the within-
294 subjects factor, and level of participation as the between-subjects effect. This was aimed at
295 determining the impact of the actions planned in the RC strategy on the variables of
296 perceived risk and awareness. Mauchly's test was applied to check the assumption of
297 sphericity. Level of involvement was categorized into three groups, specifically: *i*) those who
298 participate in one or more activities; *ii*) those who do not attend but have heard of the RC

299 strategy; and *iii*) those who have not heard of the RC strategy as the between-subjects factor.
300 Pairwise comparisons were made using the Bonferroni post hoc test. Cohen's proposed
301 commonly used guidelines were used for ranking the effect size (small, partial $\eta^2 = .01$;
302 moderate, partial $\eta^2 = .06$; large, partial $\eta^2 = .14$). Statistical significance was set at $p < .05$
303 (Cohen, 1988).

304 305 **3. RESULTS** 306

307 **3.1. Analysis of changes in risk perception and awareness**

308 309 *3.1.1. Changes in flood risk perception* 310

311 Table 4 shows the results of the t-test for paired samples in the case of the variables used to
312 measure the flood risk perception. The results only showed statistically significant differences
313 in the perception of risk in Navaluenga in the long term ($t_{(200)} = -4.61, p < .001, \eta^2 = .096$).
314 This perception was greater after the implementation of the RC strategy ($M = 3.38; SD = 1.3$)
315 than with the one obtained before conducting the said strategy ($M = 2.91; SD = 1.27$). In the
316 short term (next five years), there were no statistically significant differences in the perception
317 of risk in Navaluenga. When the focus is placed on the houses of survey participants, no
318 statistically significant differences are observed either in the short term or in the long term
319 (lifetime).

320
321 **Place Table 4 here**

322
323
324 When the analysis was carried out between the two surveys but controlling for the effect of
325 the degree of participation of the people interviewed in the activities designed in the RC

326 strategy, similar results were observed. The GLM repeated measures ANOVA revealed that
327 there were significant statistical differences in the perception of risk in Navaluenga in the long
328 term ($F(2,198) = 16.80; p < .001; \text{partial } \eta^2 = .078$), although these differences only occurred
329 among two of the three groups considered. So, post hoc Bonferroni revealed statistically
330 significant differences between the two survey periods in the case of participants who did not
331 know anything about the RC strategy and participants who were not involved in the RC
332 strategy though they knew of it. By contrast, the increase in the perception of risk in
333 Navaluenga throughout life was not statistically significant in the case of those subjects who
334 had a higher level of participation in the RC strategy activities. Fig. 3 graphically reproduces
335 these results. Data relating to the descriptive statistics of this analysis and the contrast of
336 means by post hoc Bonferroni test can be seen in Table 5.

337

338 **Place Table 5 here**

339

340 **Place Fig. 3 here**

341

342 *3.1.2. Changes in awareness*

343

344 As regards the level of awareness concerning the actions planned in the CPP before, during
345 and after a flood (Bodoque et al., 2016a), the results showed the high incidence of the RC
346 strategy, as significant statistical differences were found in the level of awareness of these
347 actions. As a result, it was concluded that there was a greater knowledge of the CPP in the
348 second survey than in the first one. Table 6 shows the results of the t-test for paired samples.

349

Place Table 6 here

350 In relation to the five categories of awareness regarding the CPP (i.e., avoidance of negative
351 consequences; evacuation routes and meeting point; self-protection behaviours; actions before

352 leaving the home; and actions after leaving the home) (Bodoque et al., 2016a), and taking into
353 consideration the levels of participation, the results of the GLM repeated measures ANOVA
354 showed the existence of statistically significant differences between the two survey periods. In
355 this regard, post hoc tests using Bonferroni correction showed a statistically significant increase
356 in awareness, except among those who had not heard of the RC strategy. After conducting the
357 RC strategy, those who had a higher level of participation in the different activities of the RC
358 strategy showed the most considerable improvement in the five categories of awareness. Fig. 4
359 graphically reproduces the results explained above. Data related to the descriptive statistics of
360 this analysis and the contrasts of means by post hoc Bonferroni test are exhibited in Table 7.

361
362 **Place Table 7 here**

363 **Place Fig. 4 here**

365 *3.1.3. Effectiveness of each action of the RC strategy*

366
367 In relation to the influence of actions on the variables of perceived risk and awareness, Table 8
368 shows that only three of them had a significant impact. Specifically, informative talks focus,
369 among other factors, on flood hazard and detailed risk maps allowed the knowledge of
370 evacuation routes and meeting points to be increased ($F(3,188) = 4.74; p < .01; \text{partial } \eta^2 =$
371 $.070$). The intergenerational workshop on past floods increased the knowledge of evacuation
372 routes and meeting points ($F(3,188) = 2.90; p < .05; \text{partial } \eta^2 = .044$) as well as actions before
373 leaving the home ($F(3,188) = 2.84; p < .05; \text{partial } \eta^2 = .045$). Finally, the contest of questions
374 and answers was the most effective action since it improved the knowledge on three of the five
375 categories considered, i.e., avoidance of negative consequences ($F(3,188) = 4.97; p < .01;$
376 $\text{partial } \eta^2 = .074$), self-protection ($F(3,188) = 5.43; p < .01; \text{partial } \eta^2 = .080$) and actions after
377 leaving the home ($F(3,188) = 4.52; p < .01; \text{partial } \eta^2 = .067$). For these significant effects, the
378 changes in the level of awareness between the two surveys are shown in Fig. 5.

379 **Place Table 8 here**

380 **Place Fig. 5 here**

381

382 **4. DISCUSSION**

383

384 **4.1. Comparison with other studies and critical assessment**

385

386 The results of this study were based on a risk dialogue approach developed through a pre-post
387 survey design, which consisted of two stages supported by a questionnaire designed ad hoc.

388 They were filled out by a statistically significant portion of the census population of the

389 municipality of Navaluenga (central Spain), both before and after the RC strategy was

390 implemented. The results obtained make it possible to argue that risk communication, based

391 on the active participation of communicators and receivers, might have a positive impact in

392 improving social resilience, as it helps to develop the local capacity to understand and take the

393 lead (Pain, 2004). So, two of the activities undertaken in the RC strategy (i.e., the

394 intergenerational workshop on past flash floods and the contest of questions and answers),

395 which involved the active participation of receivers, had a positive impact on the variables of

396 perceived risk and awareness. This shows the importance of incorporating people at the core

397 of RC as a means for raising awareness via co-producing along with experts shared

398 knowledge and outputs (Mees et al., 2016). The foregoing is in line with the findings of

399 previous research (Whitman et al., 2015; Rollason et al., 2018).

400

401 Notwithstanding the above, it should be pointed out that because this research is not a

402 laboratory experiment, causal inferences from the obtained results must be taken with caution.

403 Although some important variables, such as flood events, were deemed irrelevant during the

404 two stages of data collection (flood events never happened during either of them), there are

405 many other variables that could have escaped research control. Future similar studies should
406 be carried out to establish causal conclusions. This study also places emphasis on the link
407 between flood risk perception and RC. The analysis of the RC strategy designed to raise local
408 people's awareness has proved its effectiveness, as it has been shown that the population has
409 acquired a greater awareness of those fundamental aspects gathered in the CPP. Specifically,
410 two relevant results support this conclusion: 1) those subjects who were unaware of the RC
411 strategy did not increase their knowledge of the actions included in the CPP; 2) the change to
412 a greater understanding of the CPP was associated with the degree of involvement of the
413 participants in the RC strategy. Therefore, those who were most involved were the ones that
414 obtained a higher percentage of hits on the activities to be carried out before, during and after
415 a flood, included in the CPP. The statement above should be contrasted with future research
416 involving those permanent residents who did not participate in either of the two survey
417 processes, as well as non-permanent residents. Additionally, in future studies, a follow-up
418 should be carried out to determine whether the communication plan designed has had a long-
419 term effect on the residents of Navaluenga and to analyse the possible mediating effect that
420 awareness has had on the perception of flood risk (Lima et al., 2005).

421
422 This study has shown that well-designed RC strategies are associated with an increasing
423 public awareness of CPPs. Accordingly, CPPs may be implemented more quickly and in turn
424 will be more efficient in minimizing the effects of floods once a given event has occurred. In
425 fact, this study also shows that flood risk management in general, and CPPs in particular,
426 should not be put into practice without a guarantee of the participation of the local people.
427 This is because flood risk management based solely on a technocratic approach frequently
428 differs significantly from the risk perception of the community, which may cause flood risk
429 management to fail as the social dimension of flooding is not integrated into the management

430 process (Lara et al., 2010). Our findings are in line with the studies by Terpstra et al. (2009)
431 and Kellens et al. (2013), who concluded that RC strategies could strengthen people's risk
432 awareness, though it has only weak effects on the public's risk perception, as well as that of
433 Basic and Nuantawee (2004), who asserted that knowledge of the community's risk
434 perception is a critical issue in building effective RC strategies.

435
436 As regards flood risk perception, the averages in Table 4 show that this is greater when people
437 think of their municipality (rather than their home) and in the long term (compared to the
438 short term), and this is true for both survey 1 and 2. This finding is in line with some of the
439 cognitive bias research applied to risk perception. According to Uzzell (2000), people
440 perceive an environmental hazard as being more serious the farther away it is from them; this
441 has been labelled "environmental hyperopia". Schultz et al. (2014) also reported that the
442 seriousness of several environmental problems was perceived as being greater at a global
443 level than at a local level in 22 different countries. According to these authors, this bias is
444 based on construal level theory and the corresponding psychological distance bias (Liberman
445 and Trope, 2008). Accordingly, the interpretation of the surrounding reality becomes more
446 abstract (high-level construals) the farther away this reality is from the perceiver in terms of
447 four dimensions: Geographical or Spatial (global vs local; close vs far), Temporal (present vs
448 future), Social (similar vs different people) and Hypothetical (greater vs lower probability of
449 occurrence). The results depicted in Table 4 are in line with those Spatial (municipality vs
450 home) and Temporal (long vs short term) distance biases.

451
452 Focusing on the analysis of the RC strategy and its effects on flood risk perception, the results
453 showed a non-significant increase between the two survey periods in most cases. The only
454 statistically significant differences were detected in the perception of the risk of flooding in

455 Navaluenga in the long term, which increases in the second survey conducted after the
456 implementation of the RC strategy. Nevertheless, when the effect of participation is taken into
457 account (Fig. 3), those subjects who did not participate or who had not even heard of the RC
458 strategy were the group that increased risk perception from a statistical point of view. In other
459 words, the only group who did not increase their perception of the risk of flooding in
460 Navaluenga in the long term were those who participated in the RC strategy. The conclusion,
461 then, is that the RC strategy did not increase the flood risk perception in Navaluenga in the
462 long term.

463
464 Taking into account the finding stated some paragraphs above referring to the fact that the RC
465 strategy increased the knowledge of the CPP, the results obtained here would support those
466 found by Helweg-Larsen and Shepperd (2001) referring to another important cognitive bias:
467 the optimism bias. People are more optimistic when it comes to evaluating those negative
468 events that they believe they can control with their behaviour. When people feel competent
469 because they know how to behave in the face of a possible negative event, this is evaluated in
470 a more optimistic way. This could explain why people who participated in the RC strategy did
471 not increase their level of risk, unlike those who did not participate in it. The competence
472 obtained through participation in the RC strategy could be associated with the absence of an
473 increase in the perception of flood risk obtained in the second survey.

474 **4.2. Policy implications**

475 In compliance with the European Directive on flood risk management (60/2007/EC), the
476 different river basin districts have recently completed the first water planning cycle (2009–
477 2014). Specifically, in Spain, since transposition of the EU flood Directive to the national
478 legislation, flood risk management plans have been developed in which consideration of risk

479 perception is one of the primary objectives to be addressed. A priori, the above means a
480 significant step forward in developing sustainable flood risk management strategies, especially
481 in Spain, where risk mitigation has been mostly based on the implementation of structural
482 measures (e.g., levees, dams, and so forth). They were planned to guarantee total protection of
483 the population exposed to floods, without considering the environmental impacts of these
484 measures, or their likely downstream effects regarding increasing flood risk (Olcina et al.,
485 2016).

486
487 Although increasing risk perception is prioritized as one of the main objectives to be achieved
488 in all technical documents related to decision-making for flood risk management, the fact is the
489 above is not reflected in the implementation of specific actions with an allocated budget. By
490 way of an example, the preliminary flood risk management plan document for the Tagus River
491 hydrographic demarcation (CHT, 2014), in which the village of Navaluenga is included,
492 features as a general objective: *“improving public awareness with reference to flood
493 preparedness and response, aiming to increase flood risk perception and self-protection
494 strategies.”* The document above also provides some actions to be considered in the design of
495 risk communication strategies (e.g., informative talks or use of the Internet and media to
496 improve awareness and flood risk perception), though no specific budget allocation is provided
497 to implement them. Instead, it is hoped that some funds will be received from initiatives being
498 developed by other public organisms different to hydrographic demarcations, which are
499 developing strategies only partially related to alerts and emergency management (e.g., Spanish
500 National Meteorological Agency). An additional limitation is that the only indicators
501 considered for the control and follow-up of RC strategies are: i) some campaigns; ii) a number
502 of information days; and iii) a number of administrations including information on their web

503 pages. The shortcomings explained above have also been detected in the other hydrographic
504 plans of the Spanish hydrographic demarcations.

505

506 Given the results obtained here, prioritizing actions focused on increasing awareness through
507 the integration in CPPs of RC strategies is proposed, as their effectiveness and best cost-benefit
508 ratio has been proven. It means that risk management policies should devote specific budget
509 allocations to designing and implementing new communication strategies that are more
510 dynamic, participatory, bidirectional (Covello et al., 1986; Steelman and McCaffrey, 2013) and
511 focused on the citizens who have low risk perception and awareness (Renn, 2005). Particular
512 attention should also be paid to future policies concerning the articulation of more efficient
513 control protocols and monitoring mechanisms, such as conducting pre and post surveys (like
514 the ones performed here). Conducting periodic surveys to check how risk perception evolves is
515 also necessary.

516 As demonstrated in this study, and in line with previous research, the public participation of
517 stakeholders involved in RC can play an important role in the improvement of awareness
518 (Morss et al., 2016). Our outcomes reveal the importance of involving communities through the
519 implementation of an RC strategy enabling local people to enhance their knowledge of flood
520 risk by making this concept less abstract and more tangible, and thus contributing to improving
521 the practical actions of individuals before, during and after a flash flood.

522

523 **5. CONCLUSIONS**

524 Improvement in risk perception and awareness at the local level has been assessed through
525 implementing a risk dialogue approach based on an ad hoc RC strategy and a pre-post survey
526 design. In this study, we have, for the first time, addressed a risk perception and public

527 awareness characterization focused on improving community preparedness as an aspect to be
528 integrated into CPP. The above is of critical importance, especially in urban areas prone to
529 suffering flash floods. In such an event, floods have a quick hydrological response, in which
530 flow peaks are reached within a few hours, thereby giving little or no advance warning to
531 mitigate damage. The methodological approach deployed here enhances public awareness of
532 flood risk and mitigation measures considered in the CPP developed at Navaluenga.
533 Therefore, it may help people to understand the information they need to reduce the impact of
534 flooding on themselves and their assets. RC should be generalized and consequently
535 integrated as an essential step within flood risk management plans, which could ultimately
536 prevent, or at least reduce, flood risk, so that more reliable management in urban areas can be
537 put into practice as the EU Flood Directive requires.

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544

545

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777 **TABLE CAPTIONS**

778

779 **Table 1.** Design of the RC strategy, including the actions, the target audience and the

780 expected results

781

782 **Table 2.** Sample socio-demographic profile (N = 201)

783

784 **Table 3.** Actions that people should (according to the CPP) take before, during and after a

785 flash flood

786

787 **Table 4.** Mean differences in flood risk perception before (1) and after (2) the implementation

788 of the RC strategy

789

790 **Table 5.** Differences in lifetime risk perception in Navaluenga, depending on the level of

791 participation in the RC strategy

792

793 **Table 6.** Mean differences in the level of awareness regarding the actions to take before,

794 during and after a flash flood included in the CPP of Navaluenga (percentage of correct

795 answers)

796

797 **Table 7.** Differences in the level of awareness regarding the actions included in the CPP of

798 Navaluenga, depending on the level of participation in the RC strategy

799

800 **Table 8.** Effects of the participation level in each activity of the RC strategy on lifetime risk801 perception in Navaluenga and level of awareness ($F(3,188)$ and p -value; partial η^2 is reported

802 only for significant effects)

803 **FIGURE CAPTIONS**

804

805 **Fig. 1.** Location of the study area. Coordinate system: ETRS89, UTM Zone 30 N. There are
806 several points of conflict in the reaches studied: (i) B1 and B2 correspond to bridges on the
807 Alberche River; (ii) W is a weir also on the Alberche River; and (iii) C1 to C7 represent culverts
808 on the Alberche River and the Chorrerón Stream. These hydraulic structures increase the hazard
809 if a flood occurs.

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811 **Fig. 2.** Hazard map of Navaluenga obtained by multiplying and subsequent reclassification of
812 grids of water depth and flow velocity corresponding to the 100-year flood. These maps were
813 obtained by implementing a two-dimensional hydrodynamic model. It was based on a
814 rectangular-triangulated irregular network obtained from the digital surface model (DSM)
815 available for the study site. This DSM was derived from raw LiDAR data points with a density
816 of 0.5 points.m⁻² and an altimetric accurateness of 20 cm. Roughness was characterized from
817 official land use mapping on a scale of 1:25.000. For this purpose, the appropriate values of
818 Manning's n were assigned to every land use unit (see Bodoque et al., 2016a, b for a detailed
819 description).

820

821 **Fig. 3.** Lifetime risk perception differences depending on the level of participation in the RC
822 strategy.

823

824 **Fig. 4.** Differences in the level of awareness regarding five actions included in the CPP of
825 Navaluenga, depending on the level of participation in RC strategy. The results of the F -
826 statistic to determine significance and effect size (partial η^2) are represented for each of the
827 actions included in the CPP.

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829 **Fig. 5.** Significant differences in the level of awareness for each action of the RC strategy.

830

831 TABLES

832 Table 1

Actions	Target audience	Communication tool	Expected results
Disclose maps of flood hazard and flood risk	The whole population, including urban developers and technicians	Exposed poster in the town hall, publishing of book chapters and journal papers, uploading the flood maps to the Internet	Generalized improving of perception concerning the real flood risk situation
Informative talk	The whole population,	Oral presentation with slides	Generalized knowledge of the existence of the plan
Contest of questions-answers	Youth of school-going age (secondary education), with parents of cluster 2**	Municipal website Informational posters Email	Transfer of population from cluster 2** to cluster 3*** of risk perception
Storytelling and photographs/videotapes competitions	Adult and elderly population of cluster 1*	Municipal website Informational posters	Transfer of population from cluster 1 to cluster 2 of risk perception
Intergenerational workshop on past floods	Children and youth population	Participatory face-to-face exchange of experiences	Increased risk perception among the child population, not surveyed and never experienced a flood.

833 Notes (see details in Bodoque et al., 2016a): *Cluster 1= low-risk perception and low awareness; **Cluster 2=
 834 high-risk perception and low awareness; ***Cluster 3= high long-term risk perception and high awareness.

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837 **Table 2**

	Variables	%
Gender	Male	45.3
	Female	54.7
Age	18-34 years old	18.9
	35-54 years old	44.8
	>55 years old	36.3
Level of studies	Elementary Education	51.7
	Secondary Education	28.9
	Higher Education	19.4
Family situation	Living alone or with a partner	33.8
	Other	16.4
	Living with dependent people (children under 12 years old, elderly and / or disabled)	16.4
	Living with children 12 years old or over	33.3
Dwelling type	One-story	17.4
	Two-story	41.3
	Two-story with basement	20.4
	Apartment building	20.9
Type of resident	Temporary resident population	29.9
	Permanent resident population	70.1
Flood exposure	Floodable area	58.7
	Non-floodable area	41.3

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840 **Table 3****a) PREPAREDNESS BEHAVIORS (before flood occurrence)**

- I am informed about the level of risk
- I have a first aid box available
- I keep toxic products out of the reach of water
- I keep valuables and personal documents together in a safe place. I have a radio and torch with batteries at hand
- I make sure drainpipes and water pipes are kept clear
- I keep the outside of the house free of objects that could be washed away
- I know the location of routes and places of evacuation
- I know the location of meeting points
- I know the means to use and the tasks to be carried out by each member of the family

b) ACTIONS TAKEN DURING A POSSIBLE FLOOD

b.1) Evacuation routes and meeting points

b.2) Self-protective actions and measures to take before leaving the dwelling

- I pay attention to the alarm signal and keep the radio or television tuned for information from the Meteorological Institute or Civil Defense
- I only use the telephone to inform the authorities, for example, by ringing 112 or the municipal services
- I disconnect all electrical equipment
- I ration provisions and be sparing with heating
- I am prepared to leave the house and go to a pre-established place if you consider the situation to be dangerous or if ordered to do so by the relevant authorities

b.3) Actions before leaving the dwelling

- I gather together documentation, warm clothing, small items of value, a torch and a radio
- I disconnect the electricity, gas and water
- I do not touch electrical appliances if they are wet
- I close and lock windows and doors

c) ACTIONS TAKEN IN THE HOUSING AFTER FLOODING

- I carry out a preliminary inspection to eliminate the risk of structural collapse
- I do not drink water from the tap
- I remove animals killed by the flood
- With regard to the cleaning-up process and the consumption of foodstuffs, I follow the basic rules on health and hygiene stipulated by the relevant authority
- I begin the cleaning-up process on the upper floors
- I leave in the sidewalks or roadway (without hindering the circulation) the belongings that have been rendered unusable.
- I help the rescue and cleaning teams in the task of rehabilitating the portion of public road adjacent to my house

842 **Table 4**
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Variable	<i>M (SD)</i> (1)	<i>M (SD)</i> (2)	<i>t</i> (200)	<i>p</i>	η^2
Navaluenga in the next 5 years	2.15 (1.05)	2.08 (1.04)	0.756	.450	.003
Navaluenga in your lifetime	2.91 (1.27)	3.38 (1.30)	-4.608	<.001	.096
Your home in the next 5 years	1.40 (0.81)	1.40 (0.83)	0.079	.937	.000
Your home in your lifetime	1.72 (1.09)	1.75 (1.09)	-0.432	.666	.001

Note: 1= First survey period; 2= Second survey period.

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845 **Table 5**
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Participation Level	M (1)	M (2)	Mean differences. (1-2)	<i>N</i>
I do not know	2.82	3.42	-.60*	40
I heard something but do not participate	2.86	3.39	-.53*	109
I participate in one or more activities	3.08	3.31	-.23	52

847 Note: * $p < .01$; 1= First survey period; 2= Second survey period.

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849 **Table 6**
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Variable	<i>M (SD)</i> (1)	<i>M (SD)</i> (2)	<i>t</i> (200)	<i>p</i>	η^2
Avoidance of negative consequences	4.13 (9.18)	10.15 (14.02)	-5.531	<.001	.133
Evacuation routes and meeting point	9.55 (12.50)	18.71 (15.37)	-7.446	<.001	.217
Self-protection behaviours	9.33 (15.71)	21.64 (21.61)	-7.198	<.001	.206
Actions before leaving the home	38.64 (26.97)	54.39 (26.33)	-6.447	<.001	.172
Actions after leaving the home	15.35 (12.12)	26.23 (15.24)	-8.576	<.001	.269

Note: 1= First survey period; 2= Second survey period.

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853 **Table 7**

Awareness	Participation Level	M(1)	M(2)	Mean differences (1-2)
Avoidance of negative consequences	I do not know	2.75	4.75	-2.00
	I heard something but do not participate	3.49	10.46	-6.97*
	I Participate in one or more activities	6.54	13.65	-7.12*
Evacuation routes and meeting point	I do not know	5.50	7.00	-1.50
	I heard something but do not participate	10.28	20.00	-9.72*
	I participate in one or more activities	11.15	25.00	-13.85*
Self-protection	I do not know	8.13	10.62	-2.50
	I heard something but do not participate	8.49	22.71	-14.22*
	I participate in one or more activities	12.02	27.88	-15.86*
Actions before leaving the home	I do not know	40.83	40.00	0.83
	I heard something but do not participate	37.92	26.61	-9.30*
	I participate in one or more activities	38.46	64.10	-25.64*
Actions after leaving the home	I do not know	14.29	18.93	-4.64
	I heard something but do not participate	14.29	26.08	-11.79*
	I Participate in one or more activities	18.41	32.14	-13.73*

Note: * $p < .01$; 1= First survey period; 2= Second survey period.

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872 **Table 8**

Variable	Informative talk	Contest of questions-answers	Storytelling and photographs/videotapes competitions	Intergenerational workshop on past floods
Risk perception				
Navaluenga in your lifetime	$F= 0.40, p= .753$	$F= 1.82, p= .146$	$F= 0.16, p= .923$	$F= 1.04, p= .376$
Awareness				
Avoidance of negative consequences	$F= 0.75, p= .524$	$F= 4.97, p= .002$ (partial $\eta^2 = .074$)	$F= 2.45, p= .065$	$F= 0.28, p= .842$
Evacuation routes and meeting point	$F= 4.74, p= .003$ (partial $\eta^2 = .070$)	$F= 2.42, p= .067$	$F= 1.78, p= .153$	$F= 2.90, p= .036$ (partial $\eta^2 = .044$)
Self-protection behaviours	$F= 0.87, p= .456$	$F= 5.43, p= .001$ (partial $\eta^2 = .080$)	$F= 1.22, p= .304$	$F= 0.55, p= .650$
Actions before leaving the home	$F= 1.21, p= .308$	$F= 1.37, p= .253$	$F= 0.36, p= .780$	$F= 2.84, p= .039$ (partial $\eta^2 = .045$)
Actions after leaving the home	$F= 0.94, p= .422$	$F= 4.52, p= .004$ (partial $\eta^2 = .067$)	$F= 0.80, p= .493$	$F= 2.13, p= .097$

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875
876 The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest

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878 **ABSTRACT**

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880 Flood risk management is gradually shifting from a risk-based approach to an integrated one
881 that, among other elements, considers risk communication (RC) as a means of boosting
882 resilience. Regardless of the above, few scientists have tackled up to now the integration of
883 RC into flood risk management. In this connection, this particular study seeks to check out the
884 potential of a risk dialogue approach (based on an ad hoc RC strategy) to change attitudes and
885 behaviours in relation to flash flood risk. Via a pre-post survey design, we evaluated risk
886 perception and awareness regarding a Civil Protection Plan (CPP) implemented locally (i.e.,
887 in the municipality of Navalenguenga, central Spain). For this particular objective, a
888 questionnaire survey was created, and 201 adults (representing more than 10% of the
889 population census) were interviewed twice in a one-year period. Before the second survey, a
890 RC strategy was created. The RC strategy comprised briefings, quiz answers, storytelling, a
891 contest of videos and photographs about past floods, and an intergenerational workshop. A t-
892 test for paired sample analyses and a general linear model (GLM) repeated measures ANOVA

893 were applied to identify changes in risk perception and awareness. Our results indicate that
894 the RC strategy did increase flood risk perception in Navaluenga in the long term (lifetime).
895 Also, it increased the level of awareness of the various features that comprise the CPP,
896 enabling people to be more competent in facing a flash flood. Some cognitive biases detected
897 in the perceptual process of human beings may shed some light on the results obtained. The
898 implementation of well-thought-out RC strategies can play a role in improving resilience,
899 particularly in geographic areas such as the Iberian Peninsula, in which climate change
900 scenarios indicate a likely increase in the severity and frequency of flooding.

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Highlights

- Flash floods have a fast hydrological response giving little or no advance warning.
- Flood risk management should integrate risk communication to increase resilience.
- We assess how risk communication allows improving perception and awareness.
- Construal level theory may explain outcomes derived from risk communication.